

ORGANIZATION OF PEDAGOGICAL LESSON PROCESSES USING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: As a result of the application of information technologies to the educational process, a new database will be created, in which information such as pedagogical technologies and analytical materials will be collected. In addition, there will be many opportunities to conduct video-conferences, to show presentations of various types and to provide information about the best research works, to conduct seminars and various trainings. .

Key words: Information technology, computer system, pedagogical technology.

The use of information technologies in the management of the educational process leads to an increase in the effectiveness of education. The reason for this is the creation of opportunities to fully control the educational process and update it. For example, the presence of a local computer network in an educational institution leads to a reduction in the volume of information and documents provided on paper, which, in turn, provides an opportunity to save time when making decisions about management in the educational process. As a result of the application of information technologies to the educational process, a new database will be created, in which information such as pedagogical technologies and analytical materials will be collected. In addition, there will be many opportunities to conduct video-conferences, to show presentations of various types and to provide information about the best research works, to conduct seminars and various trainings. .

The current period is characterized as the age of information and communications. Therefore, the use of intellectual capital among labor capital and goods is one of

the most important factors.

One of the important areas of application of information technologies to the educational process is the creation of electronic educational literature, manuals and courses. Electronic educational literature and manuals provide an opportunity to enrich the lecture content and fill it with new materials. The creation of electronic educational literature and manuals, their use in the educational process requires the creation of electronic libraries in educational institutions. It can be seen that the emergence of libraries with a single catalog system in educational institutions and the creation of a local network will not only solve the problems related to libraries, but also allow to increase the efficiency and coordination of their activities.

There is no doubt that computer, information and pedagogical technologies form the basis of the distance education system. When we talk about information technologies in education, first of all, we mean didactic systems in the form of distance education, interactive pedagogy and various educational forms.

To understand the essence of the technological approach in education, first of all, it is necessary to define the meaning of the word and concept of "technology". Technology is a Greek word that means technical skill, art, logos concept, science, teaching. The concept of technology in education as a modern science that develops, improves and promotes such methods and experiences aimed at delivering the system of knowledge to students based on the curriculum and, on this basis, educating them as personnel who fully meet today's requirements is described.

In the technological approach to the educational process, it is organized as a repetitive process, the expected result of which is also described in detail and clearly recorded. The educational material is restructured and developed in accordance with the diagnostically expressed educational goals, divided into some parts. Alternative ways of delivering educational material to students are envisaged. The study of each part is controlled by the test, and the errors and shortcomings are corrected and corrected at this moment.

Pedagogical technology entered the educational process in an unconventional form, based on systematic, technological approaches with its own characteristics and features. It is a product of social-engineering thinking in pedagogy, a project of technocratic scientific thought (consciousness) in the field of education, standardization of the educational process to a certain extent, i.e. turning it into a repetitive process.

Creating a repeatable educational process in pedagogy is not an easy task. This is caused by a number of factors, such as the variety of educational tasks, the content of education and the variety of educational materials, the learning abilities of students, and the characteristics of memory. Nevertheless, scientists in developed countries have developed a method of pedagogical technology.

When using pedagogical technologies in education, it is necessary to clearly show its important features in order to highlight the difference from other methods of teaching. The study and analysis of the pedagogical literature published in our country and abroad shows that the important characteristics and signs of the pedagogical technology method should be summarized as follows:

designing the educational process on the basis of a plan in advance and re-developing this project with students in the auditorium, creating a project of the educational process that increases the educational and cognitive activities of students based on systematic, technological approaches;

The purpose of education should be complete and clear, diagnostic, objective, objective assessment of students' knowledge according to the curriculum, clarification in the form of student's observations, measurements, and actions based on the model aimed at educational goals. , the organization of the educational process based on the student's activity;

coordination of forms of education, integrity of the structure and content of the educational process, interaction on the basis of important theoretical and practical issues of pedagogy;

taking into account the interaction of technical means and human potential in the educational process;

guaranteed achievement of the planned result of education;

These include the possibility of organizing the educational system on the basis of information-pedagogical technologies and increasing its efficiency.

Each of the mentioned points has its place in the educational system, and the solution of these issues requires the use of laws of philosophy, sociology, physiology, mathematics, information, pedagogy, computer technology and other sciences.

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